

EVALUATION OF INDIAN BOOKS IN PRINT

AUTHORITY:

TITLE: Indian Books in print 2012.

SUBTITLE: A bibliography of English books published in India.

EDITOR: Sher Singh and Bhawna Singh.

FIRST EDITION: 1967.

LATEST EDITION: 2012 (24th ed.).

PUBLISHER: Indian Bibliography Bureau.

PLACE OF PUBLICATION: New Delhi.

VOLUMES: 3(in 5 parts).

LANGUAGE: English.

INTRODUCTION:

Indian books in print came in 1967 with its first edition covering the years 1952-1967. Built over four decades of experience and expertise in bibliographical control. Indian books in print constitute an authentic and reliable source of bibliographical information about Indian books published in English language. The latest edition of Indian books in print is published in 2012.

SCOPE:

- Indian books in print is a trade bibliography that contains complete bibliographical details of about 1,85,000 Indian books printed in English language till January 2012.
- It comes handy to individuals and institutions engaged in areas and in subjects relating the vast subcontinent of India.
- It includes all types of books in English language covering all subjects.

TREATMENT:

Indian books in print contains 3 volumes in 5 parts.

Volume 1: Author Index

In this volume information has been given in the following manner – author, co-author (if any), editor, compiler, title, place of publication, publisher, year of publication, number of pages, price and ISBN number.

Volume 2: Title Index

At the beginning of this volume instructions are given regarding how to use Indian books in print.

Volume 3: Subject Guide

It contains subject guide and directory of Indian publishers.

1. General works
2. Philosophy
3. Religion
4. Social science
5. Languages
6. Pure sciences
7. Technology and Useful arts
8. Fine arts
9. Literature
10. History, Bibliography and Travels
11. Bibliographies
12. India

A complete directory of Indian publishers is also provided.

While rendering the name of personal or corporate authors, rule of classified catalogue code has been followed. In case of joint authors the entry regarding the book will bear name of both the authors.

Articles 'a', 'an' and 'the' have been omitted from the title but retained where their omission would alter the sense of title.

It includes directory of Indian publisher with complete addresses and contact details. It provides complete price information which is helpful in book selection for librarians and academics.

ARRANGEMENT:

In volume 1, the name of authors is arranged alphabetically.

In volume 2, the titles are also arranged alphabetically.

In volume 3, the subject guide has been classified according to the Dewey Decimal Classification and is arranged subject wise.

FORMAT:

- It is available only in print format.
- It contains 3 volumes in 5 parts.
- It is in hardcover binding.
- The printing is clear and legible.
- Paper is of good quality.

DRAWBACK:

- It covers only those books which are published in English.
- It excludes periodicals, serials, maps, microforms, and audio- visual materials.
- It is not available in CD-ROM version.
- It does not have any online version.

CONCLUSION:

Indian books in print is an authentic and reliable source of bibliographical information about Indian books in English language. Teachers, librarians, information officers, research scholars, professors, editors and the book traders will find it a mine of valuable bibliographical information.

REFERENCES:

- Retrieved from
<http://www.saujanyabooks.com/details.aspx?id=35911>
- Retrieved from
<https://www.jainbookagency.com/newdetails.aspx?id=357>
- Indian books in print 2000.

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ASSIGNMENT ON

INDIAN BOOKS IN PRINT

DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE

PANJAB UNIVERSITY, CHANDIGARH

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